

1 **Gene discovery for detection of cancer in the breast in humans.**

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6 We compared total transcription using microarray and RNA-sequencing (published) in three separate
7 settings to discover genes whose expression could identify with authority the presence of a breast cancer
8 in humans. In one setting, we measured total transcription in tumors isolated from humans with triple
9 negative breast cancer with that of non transformed, healthy human breast. In a second setting, we
10 compared total transcription in tumors obtained from hormone receptor-positive luminal A breast cancer to
11 the normal breast to discover luminal A markers. In a third setting, we compared total transcription in the
12 hormone receptor negative PAM50 molecular subtype, basal-like, to tumors isolated from humans with
13 luminal A, luminal B and HER2+ breast cancer, enabling us to identify genes whose expression defined
14 cancer in the breast irrespective of subtype as well as genes that selectively identify basal subtype
15 cancers. Cancer markers identified belonged to families of genes encoding tumor antigens, genes
16 expressed during pregnancy or in the testis or sperm, as well as genes expressed at the cell surface in
17 non-transformed - gonadal or -embryonic settings that encode molecules of the GPR/GPRC, TMEM, FAM,
18 TTC, TMED, CDH, CEACAM, integrin, carbonic anhydrase families. Separately, genes identified as
19 markers of transformation (cancer) are likely to be expressed in tissue and context specific settings in
20 normal tissues, but which when utilized as a transformation signature in aggregate are likely to
21 conclusively and specifically identify in the breast in humans.
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1 We performed discovery of genes for scientific identification of transformation and clinical detection of
2 cancer in the human breast.

3 **Results**

4 Dataset 1: GSE45827: Genes while expression identifies hormone receptor positive cancer as compared
5 to the normal breast.

6 Dataset 2: Triple negative breast cancer (defined by specific expression in the tumor compared to the
7 breast in health). GSE185645

8 Dataset 3: Genes whose expression distinguishes cancer in patients with the basal-like subtype from the
9 the non basal like subtypes, luminal A, luminal B and HER2+. GSE45827.

10 A basal-like cancer signature.

11 GNA15
12 CDH3
13 GPRC5B
14 LRP6
15 ICAM1
16 LRP8
17 TM4SF1
18 GPR161
19 FAM135A
20 FAM210A
21 FAM49A
22 TMEM39
23 ITGB8
24 ST3GAL6
25 FAM83D
26 LRRC42
27 BRMS1L
28 SMIM13
FAM57A
TEX30
PSAT1
NAA50
TMEM26
TEX10
MFSD4A
TTC13
A2ML1
TMEM158
TMEM170A
GNB4
GPM6B

1 A basal-like cancer signature (continued).

2 TMEM200C
3 TSPAN33
4 TTC22
5 FAM64A
6 FRMD3
7 MIA
8 FAM171A
9 CT83

8 A gene expression signature for identification of luminal A, luminal B, and HER2+ breast cancers.

9 CDH11
10 TMEM45
11 FAM214A
12 LRRC32
13 TMEM106B
14 VCAN
15 TPBG
16 TMEM87
17 ITGBL1
18 FAM110B
19 TMEM150A
20 SCGB2A2
21 BCAS1
22 FAM120B
23 FAM102A
24 LGALS8
25 TMEM127
26 TMED10
27 TMRM204
28 TTC39A
FAM114A
TM7SF2
TMEM205
TMEM144
GPR39
PCDH7
TMEM167A
FAM172A
GPRC5A
TSPAN1
LRP10
TMEM87B
TSPAN31
CASC4
TSPAN15

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A gene expression signature for identification of luminal A, luminal B, and HER2+ breast cancers.
(continued).

- SPATA20
- NECTIN2
- ZG15B
- LGALS8
- TANC2
- ALCAM
- GPRC5C
- FAM13B
- TMEM62
- ICA1
- ITGB5
- TMC5
- TMBIM6
- FAM110C
- SMIM14
- CA12
- TTC8
- CA12
- MAGED2
- GPR160
- TMEM135
- FAM198B
- TSPAN13
- TMBIM3
- FAM174A
- FAM174B
- FAM214A

Discussion

As a positive control, we identified ESR1 as a gene whose expression defined non basal subtypes, and similarly for the basal subtype we identified the nuclear factor whose expression we recently demonstrated to define the tumor in human TNBC, whose expression distinguished androgen receptor AR+ and AR-triple (hormone receptor) negative breast cancer, BCL11A.